

Article

An Elegant Multi-Agent Gradient Descent for Effective Optimization in Neural Network Training and Beyond

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Abstract: Non-convex optimization problems often challenge gradient-based algorithms, such as Gradient Descent. Neural network training, a prominent application of gradient-based methods, heavily relies on their computational efficiency. However, the cost function in neural network training is typically non-convex, causing gradient-based algorithms to become trapped in local minima due to their limited exploration of the solution space. In contrast, global optimization algorithms, such as swarm-based methods, provide better exploration but introduce significant computational overhead. To address these challenges, we propose Multi-Agent Gradient Descent (MAGD), a novel algorithm that combines the efficiency of gradient-based methods with enhanced exploration capabilities. MAGD initializes multiple agents, each representing a candidate solution, and independently updates their positions using gradient-based techniques without inter-agent communication. The number of agents is dynamically adjusted by removing underperforming agents to minimize computational cost. MAGD offers a cost-effective solution for non-convex optimization problems, including but not limited to neural network training. We benchmark MAGD against traditional Gradient Descent (GD), Adam, and Swarm-Based Gradient Descent (SBGD), demonstrating that MAGD achieves superior solution quality without a significant increase in computational complexity. MAGD outperforms these methods on 20 benchmark mathematical optimization functions and 20 real-world classification and regression datasets for training shallow neural networks.

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Keywords: non-convex optimization; gradient-based algorithms; multi-agent algorithms; adaptive optimization techniques; global optimization; computational cost; Swarm-Based Gradient Descent (SBGD); neural network training; mathematical benchmark functions

1. Introduction

Optimization is a fundamental process underlying the performance of numerous scientific and engineering problems [1]. The effectiveness of an optimization method directly determines the success of its applications, as these algorithms aim to identify the best solution to a problem, assessed by a criterion known as the fitness or cost function. The primary goal in optimization is to maximize or minimize this function [2] (pp. 1–2).

A major application of optimization today lies in training machine learning models, where algorithms optimize the weights of neural networks. Among the most widely used optimization techniques for neural networks are gradient-based algorithms, including Gradient Descent (GD) and its variants, such as Momentum, Adagrad, and Adam [3]. Despite their longstanding use, these algorithms remain robust and efficient, often outperforming many newer alternatives, particularly in high-dimensional applications such as machine

and deep learning [4] (p. 2). Their enduring popularity stems from their computational efficiency and adaptability to diverse problems.

However, gradient-based algorithms typically assume a convex cost function with a single optimal solution [5]. This assumption often fails in real-world applications [6] (p. 33), where non-convex functions exhibit multiple local minima and maxima. While local optima may suffice in some cases, this limitation can significantly impact performance in others [7] (pp. 6–7). Additionally, algorithms like GD and Adam are sensitive to initial conditions [8], restricting their ability to explore the solution space thoroughly.

To overcome these limitations, researchers have explored multi-start methods, which initiate optimization from multiple starting points to increase the likelihood of finding better solutions. These approaches, however, often incur high computational costs and require careful resource allocation [9] (p. 13), and they still may not guarantee finding the global optimum [10] (p. 455).

Swarm-based algorithms, such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [11], have demonstrated strong global optimization capabilities. Nevertheless, these methods face challenges such as the curse of dimensionality [12] and high computational overhead [13] (p. 112), which limit their applicability in complex domains like deep learning [14] (pp. 14093–14094). Hybrid approaches that combine the global exploration of swarm algorithms with the local refinement of gradient-based methods, often termed swarm-based gradient methods [15] or gradient-based swarm algorithms [16], show promise but require further validation in high-dimensional settings [17] (p. 34).

In this paper, we present Multi-Agent Gradient Descent (MAGD), a novel multi-start algorithm designed to address the limitations of traditional gradient-based methods. MAGD provides an efficient multi-start framework with a simple implementation. By simultaneously updating multiple agents and dynamically removing underperforming ones, MAGD reduces computational costs while enhancing performance. Additionally, it integrates the Adam updating rule, accelerating convergence in complex landscapes.

1.1. Contributions of the Paper

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

1. **A Streamlined and Efficient Multi-Start Algorithm:** We propose the MAGD algorithm as a multi-start approach that simplifies optimization by accelerating agent termination and leveraging the Adam updating rule to enhance convergence.
2. **Performance Evaluation:** We evaluate MAGD on 20 benchmark mathematical optimization functions and apply it to train shallow neural networks on 20 real-world classification and regression datasets, statistically demonstrating its superiority over traditional gradient-based and swarm-based gradient methods.
3. **Efficiency in Execution Time:** We provide both theoretical and empirical evidence demonstrating that the algorithm introduces minimal time overhead, making it efficient and scalable for high-dimensional optimization tasks where the dimensionality or number of iterations greatly exceeds the number of agents.

1.2. Structure of the Paper

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work on optimization algorithms, emphasizing the history of Gradient Descent (GD), its evolution, and the developments leading to modern variants. Section 3 presents the preliminaries, including the fundamentals of GD and the Adam optimization algorithm. Section 4 introduces the proposed MAGD algorithm in detail. Section 5 describes the experimental setup and results, comparing MAGD's performance with GD, Adam, and Swarm-Based Gradient Descent (SBGD) on benchmark optimization problems and neural network training

tasks. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by summarizing the theoretical and empirical findings, discussing research limitations, and providing recommendations for future work.

1.3. Abbreviations and Acronyms

- GD: Gradient Descent
- Adam: Adaptive Moment Estimation Gradient Descent
- MAGD: Multi-Agent Gradient Descent
- FMA: Fixed Multi-Agent Adam
- SBGD: Swarm-Based Gradient Descent

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Development of Gradient Descent: Early Roots and Its Resurgence Through Backpropagation

The earliest concept of iterative methods for optimization can be traced back to Isaac Newton, who laid the groundwork for both calculus and optimization techniques [18]. Following Newton, the notable mathematician Augustin-Louis Cauchy made significant contributions to numerical analysis, including methods for solving optimization problems. In 1847, Cauchy [19] developed the method of steepest descent, an early form of gradient descent. His work focused on finding the minimum of a function by iteratively moving in the direction of the negative gradient, which points towards the steepest descent. In 1908, Jacques Hadamard further explored the steepest descent method in the context of variational calculus [20]. In 1958, Rosenblatt [21] developed the perceptron, an early application of gradient descent in machine learning. The resurgence of interest in neural networks in the 1980s, particularly with the development of the backpropagation algorithm by Rumelhart et al. [22], marked a pivotal moment for gradient descent, as it became the foundation for backpropagation in neural network training.

2.2. Literature Work on Mitigating the Gradient Descent Local Optima Problem

The Gradient Descent algorithm assumes that the objective function is convex [5], meaning it has only one optimum (either a minimum or a maximum), which is the global optimum. However, in many cases, this assumption does not hold, and Gradient Descent can fall into local minima, limiting its capability to find better solutions. The problem of suboptimality that gradient descent suffers from has been extensively discussed, and considerable research has been dedicated to mitigating this issue.

Bottou and Léon [23] worked on Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) in 1991 and highlighted its ability to escape local minima by introducing noise into the gradient updates. In 2015, Dauphin et al. [24] proposed methods to identify and escape from saddle points, which can be even more problematic than local minima in high-dimensional spaces. Additionally, in 2014, Kingma et al. [25] improved stochastic gradient descent using adaptive learning rates that help escape local minima more effectively in deep learning models, coining the term Adam. In 2019, Chaudhari et al. [26] introduced Entropy-SGD, a novel approach that biases gradient descent towards flat minima, which are thought to generalize better and are less likely to be local minima.

2.3. Restart Gradient Descent Algorithms

Restart gradient-based algorithms attempt to escape local minima by restarting the search process from scratch, a method referred to as a cold restart, or partially, known as a warm restart [27] (p. 46). An earlier paper by Ros in 2009 [28] proposed a cold restart strategy for repeatedly applying the gradient descent algorithm from different initial positions based on specific criteria. This approach increases the ability to find better local or even global optima, albeit with a computational penalty.

Loshchilov et al. in 2016 [29] proposed a warm restart algorithm called Stochastic Gradient Descent with Restarts (SGDR). SGDR allows the learning rate to reset at specified time intervals, providing the model with opportunities to jump from one local minimum to another. Other restart methods involve adaptive techniques, where the decision to restart is based on specific criteria, such as the norm of the gradient or the progress made in reducing the cost function, as suggested by Fercoq et al. [30].

While restart strategies have shown promise, they can introduce additional computational costs due to the necessity for multiple restarts.

2.4. Multi-Start Gradient Descent Algorithms

A recently common method for mitigating the suboptimality problem in gradient-based algorithms is multi-start gradient-based optimization. This approach involves initiating different potential solutions from various positions in the cost function landscape and running the gradient-based search for all potential solutions simultaneously, rather than sequentially as seen in restart-based algorithms. This method helps escape local optima with less computational effort. However, running multiple instances of the algorithm simultaneously raises concerns about execution time penalties, which motivates research into improving the computational efficiency of multi-start algorithms. For instance, Peri et al. in 2012 [31] introduced the idea of replacing the computationally expensive cost function with a surrogate model. While this approach is innovative, it still requires the additional step of fitting the surrogate model. Another issue that increases the complexity of this algorithm is the use of de-clustering for the initialization of potential solutions, which itself represents an extra computational cost and complicates implementation. In 2021, Žilinskas et al. [10] developed an algorithm called METHOD (Multi-start with Early Termination Of Descents), which is similar to sequential restart algorithms but incorporates memory, terminating any new point that belongs to an already explored region. However, the sequential updating of instances and the iterations needed for the local search of each instance can significantly increase execution time. Additionally, there are computational costs associated with checking whether each instance is located in an already explored region, alongside the extra hyperparameter tuning required to control this process.

2.5. Swarm-Based Optimization Algorithms and Their Application as Alternatives to Gradient Descent in Neural Network Training

Swarm-based algorithms are a subset of metaheuristic optimization techniques inspired by the collective behavior of decentralized, self-organized systems found in nature [32], such as flocks of birds, schools of fish, and colonies of ants. These algorithms have proven effective in solving complex optimization problems, particularly those that are difficult to address with traditional methods [33] (p. 1627).

One of the earliest swarm-based algorithms, the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), was introduced by Dorigo et al. in 1996 [34], inspired by the foraging behavior of ants. Similarly, the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm was developed by Kennedy et al. in 1995 [11], drawing inspiration from the social behavior of bird flocks and fish schools. Karaboğa et al. [35] developed the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm in 2005, which is inspired by the foraging behavior of honeybees. Another effective algorithm for global optimization problems is the Cuckoo Search (CS) algorithm, introduced by Yang et al. in 2009 [36]. This algorithm employs Lévy flights to enhance global search capabilities, thereby effectively avoiding local minima. The Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO), introduced by Mirjalili et al. in 2014 [37], mimics the leadership hierarchy and encircling behavior of wolf packs to balance exploration and exploitation during the search for optimal solutions.

Numerous researchers have explored the application of swarm-based optimizers as alternatives to gradient descent algorithms for various local optimal problems. Yang et al. [36]

tested the CS and PSO algorithms on multiple benchmark mathematical functions with multiple local minima, demonstrating their efficiency in finding better solutions. In 2010, Yang et al. [38] introduced the BAT algorithm, proving its effectiveness in identifying global optima. Similarly, Mirjalili et al. [37] validated the efficiency of the GWO algorithm for problems with multiple local optima.

In 2019, Khan et al. [39] developed a new algorithm called HACPSO, derived from APSO and CS algorithms, specifically for training artificial neural networks (ANNs). Their findings indicated that the proposed algorithms outperform the backpropagation (BP) algorithm, albeit with increased execution time. In 2020, Turkoglu et al. [40] employed the Artificial Algae Algorithm (AAA) [41] for training ANNs, concluding that while AAA outperformed BP in terms of accuracy, it was slower in terms of convergence speed. Eker et al. [42] further demonstrated that swarm-based algorithms can achieve superior results in training neural networks.

However, swarm-based algorithms often incur higher computational costs in high-dimensional problems. This increased cost, commonly referred to as the curse of dimensionality, arises from the exponential growth of the search space with increasing dimensions, compounded by the swarm's stochastic nature and large swarm size [12]. To address this challenge, several studies have proposed hybrid swarm–gradient methods that combine the global exploration capabilities of swarm algorithms with the efficient convergence properties of gradient-based approaches.

2.6. Hybrid Swarm–Gradient Descent Algorithms

Noel et al. [16] introduced a gradient-based PSO algorithm in which the global best solution performs localized searches using gradient descent. This hybrid approach improves solution quality but significantly increases execution time due to the combined computational demands of random searching and gradient descent steps.

Lu et al. [15] proposed a swarm-based gradient descent algorithm for global optimization. The algorithm initializes a swarm of potential solutions, which communicate and update their positions through gradient descent. As iterations progress, less promising solutions are removed, and closely positioned solutions are merged, reducing computational costs. However, the algorithm remains computationally intensive due to the need for step-size optimization at every iteration, its complex implementation, and extensive hyperparameter tuning requirements.

He et al. [43] developed a compact cat swarm optimization algorithm based on a Small Sample Probability Model (SSPCCSO). This algorithm combines swarm and gradient-based methods by using a compact representation of the swarm, where only a single cat move is stored at each iteration according to gradient descent principles. New cats are sampled using a probability model that adjusts based on fitness evaluations. Despite its promise for computational efficiency, SSPCCSO has yet to be tested on real-world applications, such as neural network training.

From our narrative literature review, we can conclude the following:

- Gradient-based algorithms are among the most practical optimization methods for high-dimensional problems; however, they often fail to reach the global optimal solution.
- Adaptive learning rates and momentum in gradient-based algorithms have been employed to mitigate suboptimal solutions but still leave room for further enhancement.
- Restart-based gradient algorithms incur higher computational costs, particularly in the case of a cold restart, where optimization begins from a completely new initial point.
- Multi-start algorithms in the literature are often complex to implement due to additional sub-procedures, such as clustering, fitting surrogate models, and memory management.

- Swarm-based algorithms often struggle with the curse of dimensionality, making them impractical for high-dimensional problems like neural network training.
- Hybrid swarm–gradient algorithms in the literature may offer improved global optimization capabilities but often come with higher computational costs, greater implementation complexity, and numerous hyperparameters that are difficult to tune.

3. Preliminaries

3.1. Gradient Descent Algorithm Overview

This section provides a brief overview of the traditional gradient descent algorithm. Gradient Descent (GD) is an iterative optimization algorithm designed for problems with differentiable cost functions. GD updates the solution by moving in the opposite direction of the cost function's gradient with respect to each dimension. The update rule is expressed as:

$$x_{t+1} = x_t - \alpha \nabla_x f(x_t),$$

where x_t represents the parameters at iteration t , α is the learning rate, and $\nabla_x f(x_t)$ is the gradient of the cost function f with respect to x . The learning rate α controls the step size. The full algorithm is outlined in Algorithm 1. By iteratively moving against the gradient, the variables aim to reach the minimum of the function.

However, GD faces challenges in flat regions or saddle points, where the gradient approaches zero, resulting in minimal updates and premature convergence. Researchers have continuously worked on improving GD to overcome these limitations.

Algorithm 1: Gradient Descent Algorithm

Input: Initial parameters x_0 , learning rate α , and cost function $f(x)$

Output: Optimized parameters x_{best}

Initialize x and $t \leftarrow 0$;

while *not converged* **do**

Compute the gradient $\nabla f(x_t)$;

Update the parameters $x_{t+1} \leftarrow x_t - \alpha \nabla f(x_t)$;

return Optimized parameters x_{best} ;

3.2. Adam Algorithm Overview

The Adam algorithm [25] addresses the limitations of gradient descent and is widely used in neural network training. Adam improves upon GD by adaptively adjusting the learning rate based on the gradient's history. This adjustment preserves the directionality of useful gradients while scaling step sizes using gradient variance to ensure stability.

Adam maintains two exponential moving averages: the first momentum term, m , tracks the gradient's history, while the second term, v , tracks the variance. These moments are updated as follows:

$$m^{(t+1)} = \beta_1 m^{(t)} + (1 - \beta_1) \nabla f^{(t)} \quad (1)$$

$$v^{(t+1)} = \beta_2 v^{(t)} + (1 - \beta_2) \nabla f^{(t)} \quad (2)$$

where $\nabla f^{(t)}$ is the gradient, and $\beta_1, \beta_2 \in [0, 1]$ control the decay rates of the moving averages. To correct the initial bias, the moments are scaled by $(1 - \beta_1^t)$ and $(1 - \beta_2^t)$.

The momentum mechanism in Adam reduces the likelihood of getting stuck in local minima by maintaining directional consistency. However, Adam remains sensitive to initial conditions, and its effectiveness depends on hyperparameter tuning and the landscape of the cost function.

4. Proposed Solution

To address the challenge of local minima in gradient descent algorithms while minimizing computational penalties, we propose an elegant algorithm, the Multi-Agent Gradient Descent (MAGD), as a simplified variant of multi-start methods. The MAGD algorithm is inspired by Occam's Razor [44], aiming to deliver a solution that is both simple and competitive.

MAGD initializes weight vectors for gradient descent, distributing them uniformly across the search space. Over time, the algorithm selects the most promising vector and removes less effective ones, thereby reducing the computational burden. This approach ensures that most search agents are eliminated within the initial iterations, allowing MAGD to transition smoothly into a standard gradient descent process, which serves as an efficient heuristic initialization method. This design achieves a balance between solution quality and computational simplicity.

4.1. Main Characteristics of the Multi-Agent Gradient Descent Algorithm (MAGD)

The Multi-Agent Gradient Descent (MAGD) algorithm incorporates the following key features:

1. **Multi-Agent Initialization:** The algorithm begins by generating a set of uniformly distributed initial solutions in the search space, each termed an "agent". The initialization is performed according to Equation (3):

$$x_i \sim \mathcal{U}(x), \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, N_{\text{agents}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathcal{U}(x)$ denotes the uniform distribution, ensuring equal sampling probability across the search space. Since there is typically no prior information about regions more likely to contain the optima, a uniform distribution is preferred. However, if domain-specific knowledge is available, other distributions tailored to the problem may be used. Here, x represents the search space, and N_{agents} is the number of initial agents.

2. **Adam Updating Rule Integration:** Building on the substantial improvements demonstrated by the Adam algorithm [25], MAGD incorporates its position-update rule (Equations (1) and (2)) for each agent. This integration enhances the exploratory power of individual agents, contributing to the overall efficiency of the algorithm.
3. **Adaptive Agent Pruning:** Adaptive Agent Pruning is the most indispensable feature of MAGD for maintaining computational efficiency. This mechanism eliminates non-promising agents, significantly reducing execution time while preserving the exploration benefits of diverse initial positions. It employs two distinct strategies:
 - (a) **Convergence-Based Agent Reduction:** As iterations progress, MAGD evaluates each agent's convergence status. Converged agents with inferior performance are removed. Convergence is determined by a negligible change in cost over a specified period T_{conv} , expressed as:

$$\text{Converged} = \|f^{(t+T_{\text{conv}})} - f^{(t)}\| < \epsilon_{\text{conv}}, \quad (4)$$

where $f^{(t)}$ and $f^{(t+T_{\text{conv}})}$ represent the agent's cost at iterations t and $t + T_{\text{conv}}$, respectively. ϵ_{conv} is a small threshold (e.g., 0.001). It is important to recall that the removal of agents is performed with caution to ensure that the best agent is not lost. This principle aligns with the overarching goal of maintaining the quality of solutions during the pruning process.

- (b) **Periodic Performance-Based Reduction:** At fixed intervals (T_{red}), agents with costs above the mean cost are pruned. This interval is a hyperparameter, typically set to a small fraction of the maximum iterations, such as 1%. Periodic reduction

accelerates computational efficiency. The pruning process is disabled once only one agent remains, thereby eliminating the additional computational complexity associated with this process, while the remaining agent continues to search for the global optimum, albeit without a guarantee of success.

Stopping Criteria: The stopping criteria can be tailored to the specific problem and may include reaching the maximum number of iterations, detecting convergence, or satisfying another user-defined condition. In our implementation, the algorithm terminates upon convergence of the best solution or reaching the maximum iteration count.

The pseudocode for MAGD is detailed in Algorithm 2. The inputs include the following:

Algorithm 2: MAGD Algorithm

Input: T_{conv} , ϵ_{conv} , T_{red} , N_{agents} , $f(x)$, t_{max} , α , β_1 , β_2 , ϵ

Output: x_{best}

Initialize agents $x_i^{(0)} \sim \mathcal{U}(X)$, for $i = 1, \dots, N_{agents}$;

Initialize $m_i^{(0)} \leftarrow 0$, $v_i^{(0)} \leftarrow 0$, for $i = 1, \dots, N_{agents}$;

for $t \leftarrow 1$ **to** t_{max} **do**

foreach agent x_i **do**

$\nabla f_i^{(t)} = \nabla f(x_i^{(t)})$; // Compute gradient

$m_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \beta_1 m_i^{(t)} + (1 - \beta_1) \nabla f_i^{(t)}$; // Equation (1)

$v_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \beta_2 v_i^{(t)} + (1 - \beta_2) (\nabla f_i^{(t)})^2$; // Equation (2)

$\hat{m}_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \frac{m_i^{(t+1)}}{1 - \beta_1^t}$, $\hat{v}_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \frac{v_i^{(t+1)}}{1 - \beta_2^t}$;

$x_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow x_i^{(t)} - \alpha \frac{\hat{m}_i^{(t+1)}}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_i^{(t+1)} + \epsilon}}$;

$f_i^{(t+1)} \leftarrow f(x_i^{(t+1)})$; // Update cost

$x_{best} \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_x (f^{(t+1)})$; // Update best agent

 // Removing underperformed agents

if $t > T_{conv}$ **then**

foreach agent x_i **do**

$\text{Converged}_i \leftarrow (\|f_i^{(t)} - f_i^{(t-T_{conv})}\|_1 < \epsilon_{conv})$;

if Converged_i ;

 & $(f_i^{(t+1)} > f_{best}^{(t+1)})$ **then**

 Remove agent x_i ; $N_{agents} \leftarrow N_{agents} - 1$;

 // Periodic reduction procedure

if $t \bmod T_{red} = 0$ **then**

$\bar{f}^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \frac{1}{N_{agents}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{agents}} f_i^{(t+1)}$; // Compute the mean cost

foreach agent x_i **do**

if $f_i^{(t+1)} > \bar{f}^{(t+1)}$ **then**

 Remove agent x_i ; $N_{agents} \leftarrow N_{agents} - 1$;

 // Terminate the algorithm if it converged

if $\|f_{best}^{(t+1)} - f_{best}^{(t)}\|_1 < \epsilon_{conv}$ **then**

Terminate the algorithm and output x_{best} ;

else

 Update $t \leftarrow t + 1$ and continue the next iteration

return x_{best} ;

- x : Search space.
- $f(x)$: Cost function to minimize.
- $\alpha \in (0, 1]$: Learning rate (typically less than 0.3).
- $\beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1]$: Exponential decay rates for Adam (default values: 0.9, 0.999).
- ϵ : Small constant to prevent division by zero in Adam.
- t_{\max} : Maximum number of iterations.
- N_{agents} : Initial number of agents.
- $T_{\text{conv}} \in [1, t_{\max}]$: Iterations after which convergence is checked. A smaller value reduces computational cost but may compromise solution quality (default: between 1 and 10).
- ϵ_{conv} : Threshold for agent convergence (default: 0.0001).
- $T_{\text{red}} \in [1, t_{\max}]$: Interval for periodic agent reduction. This value should be significantly smaller than t_{\max} to facilitate faster pruning.

4.2. Time and Space Complexity Analysis of MAGD

4.2.1. Time Complexity

Gradient Computation and Update

The time complexity in each iteration arises from gradient computation and position updates. For each agent, computing the gradient and updating its position requires $O(d)$, where d is the dimensionality of the agent's position. Given N_t agents at iteration t , the per-iteration complexity is:

$$T(t) = O(d \cdot N_t). \tag{5}$$

For a single agent ($N_t = 1$, for all iterations) over t_{\max} iterations, the total complexity is:

$$\sum_{t=0}^{t_{\max}-1} T(t) = t_{\max} \cdot T(t) = t_{\max} \cdot d. \tag{6}$$

For a constant number of agents N across all iterations:

$$\sum_{t=0}^{t_{\max}-1} T(t) = t_{\max} \cdot T(t) = t_{\max} \cdot d \cdot N. \tag{7}$$

In MAGD, the number of agents N_t at iteration t decreases exponentially as $t \rightarrow t_{\max}$. Agents with costs worse than the mean are removed after every T_{red} iterations (convergence-based reduction is omitted because it cannot be reliably expected.). Assuming a fixed reduction factor $r \in (0, 1]$, representing the fraction of agents retained, the number of agents after each reduction step can be approximated as:

$$N_k = \begin{cases} N_0 \cdot r^k, & \text{if } N_k > 1, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

where $k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor t_{\max}/T_{\text{red}} \rfloor\}$ corresponds to reduction steps.

For each interval $t \in [k \cdot T_{\text{red}}, (k + 1) \cdot T_{\text{red}})$, the number of agents N_k remains constant. The total duration per interval is:

$$T_k = T_{\text{red}} \cdot d \cdot N_k. \tag{9}$$

With $\lfloor t_{\max}/T_{\text{red}} \rfloor$ intervals, the total time complexity is:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor t_{\max}/T_{\text{red}} \rfloor - 1} T_k = d \cdot T_{\text{red}} \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor t_{\max}/T_{\text{red}} \rfloor - 1} N_k. \tag{10}$$

Substituting N_k from Equation (8) into Equation (10), we obtain:

$$T \approx d \cdot T_{red} \cdot \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor - 1} N_0 \cdot r^k. \tag{11}$$

The summation $\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor - 1} N_0 \cdot r^k$ is a geometric series:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor - 1} N_0 \cdot r^k = \begin{cases} N_0 \cdot \frac{1-r^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor}}{1-r}, & r < 1, \\ N_0 \cdot \lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor, & r = 1. \end{cases} \tag{12}$$

Assuming $r < 1$, the series converges to:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor - 1} N_0 \cdot r^k = N_0 \cdot \frac{1-r^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor}}{1-r}. \tag{13}$$

Substituting Equation (13) into Equation (11), the final time complexity is:

$$O(d, N_0, t_{max}) = d \cdot T_{red} \cdot N_0 \cdot \frac{1-r^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor}}{1-r}. \tag{14}$$

For $t_{max} \gg T_{red}$, where $r^{\lfloor t_{max}/T_{red} \rfloor} \rightarrow 0$, this simplifies to:

$$O(d, N_0, t_{max}) = d \cdot T_{red} \cdot N_0 \cdot \frac{1}{1-r}. \tag{15}$$

Assuming $N_0 \gg \frac{1}{1-r}$ the time complexity further simplifies to:

$$O(d, N_0, t_{max}) = d \cdot t_{max} \cdot N_0. \tag{16}$$

Because $T_{red} = \rho \cdot t_{max}$, where $\rho \in (0, 1]$.

When $t_{max} \gg N_0$, or $d \gg N_0$, the time complexity becomes:

$$O(d, t_{max}) = d \cdot t_{max}. \tag{17}$$

A comparison of (6) and (17) reveals that, as $t_{max} \gg N_0$, or $d \gg N_0$, the time complexity of MAGD converges to that of a single-agent algorithm.

4.2.2. Space Complexity

Each agent requires $O(d)$ space to store its position, gradient, moments, and auxiliary variables. At iteration t , the total space complexity is:

$$\text{Space}(d, N_t) = O(d \cdot N_t). \tag{18}$$

For the maximum number of agents N_0 , the maximum space complexity is:

$$\text{Space}_{max}(d, N_0) = O(d \cdot N_0). \tag{19}$$

From Equation (8), as $t \rightarrow t_{max}$, $N_t \rightarrow 1$. Therefore, the final space complexity can be expressed as:

$$\text{Space}(d) = O(d). \tag{20}$$

Exponential Decay of Storage

While the space complexity of MAGD is $\text{Space}(d) = O(d)$, indicating no significant penalty for larger initial agent counts N_0 in terms of Big-O notation, a practical penalty

exists. However, MAGD incorporates a mechanism that exponentially reduces storage requirements over time, as described by Equation (8). This ensures that storage remains manageable throughout the optimization process.

Fixed Multi-Agent Adam

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the adaptive agent reduction process, we implemented the standard Adam algorithm with the same number of agents as MAGD but without the reduction process. This implementation, referred to as Fixed Multi-Agent Adam (FMA), serves as a straightforward application of Adam to multiple agents and is used solely for comparison.

5. Experiments and Results

5.1. Experimental Setup and Implementation Details

In this section, we present the experiments conducted and discuss the results obtained from the implementation of our algorithm.

The experiments were performed on a Kaggle online server equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU @ 2.2 GHz (manufactured by Intel Corporation, Santa Clara, CA, USA), featuring 4 physical cores and 2 threads per core, providing a total of 8 logical cores. The server has 32 GB of RAM and does not utilize GPUs. All algorithms were implemented in Python.

The algorithm has been benchmarked against GD, Adam, and SBGD. These choices are deliberate and well-founded: GD represents the foundational approach for gradient-based optimization and is a natural baseline. Adam, in contrast, is currently the dominant algorithm in machine learning optimization. SBGD was included due to its shared characteristics with MAGD, as both are multi-agent-based and incorporate strategies for agent reduction. However, important differences exist between the two. SBGD is a swarm-based algorithm that relies on inter-agent communication, which introduces additional computational overhead and increases the number of hyperparameters requiring fine-tuning. These hyperparameters are often interdependent, complicating their adjustment and making the overall implementation of SBGD more challenging. By contrast, MAGD avoids inter-agent communication entirely, significantly reducing computational complexity, minimizing hyperparameter requirements, and enhancing implementation simplicity.

For MAGD, FMA, and SBGD, the agent updates in each iteration were executed sequentially (without explicit parallelization). However, simultaneous updates of agents were achieved by leveraging the vectorization capabilities of the NumPy library. This approach utilized SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) operations to optimize memory access and execution time per core, effectively avoiding the overhead associated with Python for loops.

The execution time for each algorithm was measured by recording the timestamp at the start and end of the execution using the Python time library. The complete implementation code is provided in the Supplementary Material.

5.2. Mathematical Functions Experiments and Results

The proposed MAGD algorithm was tested on 20 benchmark mathematical functions for optimization. These functions are summarized in Table 1. All functions were evaluated in two dimensions and are non-convex, meaning they have multiple local minima. MAGD was implemented to find the minimum values of these functions and was compared to GD, Adam, and Swarm-Based Gradient Descent (SBGD) [15].

Table 1. Benchmark functions for optimization: formulas, ranges, and minimum values f^* .

Function Name	Formula	Domain Range	f^*
Rastrigin Function	$f(x) = 10n + \sum_{i=1}^n [x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i)]$	$[-5.12, 5.12]$	0
Ackley Function	$f(x) = -20 \exp\left(-0.2\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2}\right) - \exp\left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(2\pi x_i)\right) + 20 + e$	$[-32.768, 32.768]$	0
Goldstein–Price Function	$f(x, y) = [1 + (x + y + 1)^2 \cdot (19 - 14x + 3x^2 - 14y + 6xy + 3y^2)] \cdot [30 + (2x - 3y)^2 \cdot (18 - 32x + 12x^2 + 48y - 36xy + 27y^2)]$	$[-2, 2]$	3
Levy Function N.13	$f(x) = \sin^2(\pi w_1) + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (w_i - 1)^2 [1 + 10 \sin^2(\pi w_i + 1)] + (w_n - 1)^2 [1 + \sin^2(2\pi w_n)]$	$[-10, 10]$	0
Himmelblau Function	$f(x, y) = (x^2 + y - 11)^2 + (x + y^2 - 7)^2$	$[-5, 5]$	0
Three-Hump Camel Function	$f(x, y) = 2x^2 - 1.05x^4 + \frac{x^6}{6} + xy + y^2$	$[-5, 5]$	0
Griewank Function	$f(x) = 1 + \frac{1}{4000} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 - \prod_{i=1}^n \cos\left(\frac{x_i}{\sqrt{i}}\right)$	$[-600, 600]$	0
Cross-in-Tray Function	$f(x, y) = -0.0001 \left(\left \sin(x) \sin(y) \exp\left(\left 100 - \frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{\pi} \right \right) \right + 1 \right)^{0.1}$	$[-10, 10]$	-2.06261
Eggholder Function	$f(x, y) = -(y + 47) \sin\left(\sqrt{ x/2 + (y + 47) }\right) - x \sin\left(\sqrt{ x - (y + 47) }\right)$	$[-512, 512]$	-959.6407
Michalewicz Function	$f(x) = -\sum_{i=1}^n \sin(x_i) \left[\sin\left(\frac{ix_i^2}{\pi}\right) \right]^{2m}$	$[0, \pi]$	-1.8013 (for n = 10)
Alpine Function	$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sin(x_i) + 0.1x_i $	$[0, 10]$	0
Schaffer Function N.2	$f(x, y) = 0.5 + \frac{\sin^2(x^2 - y^2) - 0.5}{(1 + 0.001(x^2 + y^2))^2}$	$[-100, 100]$	0
Schaffer Function N.4	$f(x, y) = 0.5 + \frac{\cos^2(\sin(x^2 + y^2)) - 0.5}{(1 + 0.001(x^2 + y^2))^2}$	$[-100, 100]$	0
Easom Function	$f(x, y) = -\cos(x) \cos(y) \exp(-[(x - \pi)^2 + (y - \pi)^2])$	$[-100, 100]$	-1
Shubert Function	$f(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^5 i \cos[(i + 1)x + i] \sum_{j=1}^5 j \cos[(j + 1)y + j]$	$[-10, 10]$	-186.7309
Schwefel Function	$f(x) = 418.9829n - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \sin\left(\sqrt{ x_i }\right)$	$[-500, 500]$	0
Zettl Function	$f(x, y) = (x^2 + y^2 - 2x)^2 + \frac{x}{4}$	$[-5, 10]$	-0.003791
Leon Function	$f(x, y) = 100(y - x^2)^2 + (1 - x)^2$	$[-1.2, 1.2]$	0
Drop-Wave Function	$f(x, y) = -\frac{1 + \cos(12\sqrt{x^2 + y^2})}{0.5(x^2 + y^2) + 2}$	$[-5.12, 5.12]$	-1
Langermann Function	$f(x) = -\sum_{i=1}^m c_i \exp\left(-\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - a_{ij})^2\right) \cos\left[\pi \sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - a_{ij})^2\right]$	$[0, 10]$	-4.155

The hyperparameters used for all algorithms in these experiments are summarized in Table 2. The learning rate of SBGD is initially set to 3, as recommended by the authors in their research, to ensure it is sufficiently large [15] (p. 9), as the specified value reflects the initial learning rate rather than its adaptive adjustments during the iterations. Tables 3 and 4 detail the hyperparameters specific to MAGD and SBGD, respectively.

The exclusive SBGD hyperparameters are described as follows:

- $tol_{mrg} \in [0, 1]$: This parameter determines the merging of agents that satisfy $\|x_i - x_j\|_1 < tol_{mrg}$ at each iteration, where $i, j = 1, \dots, N_{agents}$ and $i \neq j$.
- $tol_m \in [0, 1]$: This threshold dictates the preservation of agents based on their *mass*. Agents with $mass < (tol_m / N_{agents})$ are removed. Here, *mass* is a term in SBGD proportional to the solution quality.
- $tol_{res} \in [0, 1]$: This parameter is equivalent to ϵ_{conv} in MAGD and represents the convergence tolerance.
- λ and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$: These parameters control the learning rate updating procedure in SBGD. For further details, refer to [15].

Table 2. Hyperparameters setting for All Algorithms in mathematical benchmark functions experiments.

Algorithm	N_{agents}	α	β_1	β_2	ϵ_{conv}	ϵ
GD	1	0.01	-	-	10^{-4}	-
Adam	1	0.01	0.9	0.999	10^{-4}	10^{-8}
FMA	100	0.01	0.9	0.999	10^{-4}	10^{-8}
MAGD	100	0.01	0.9	0.999	10^{-4}	10^{-8}
SBGD	100	3.00	-	-	10^{-4}	-

Table 3. Setting of the exclusive Hyperparameters for MAGD in mathematical benchmark functions experiments.

Parameter	Value
T_{conv}	1
T_{red}	3

Table 4. Setting of the exclusive Hyperparameters for SBGD in mathematical benchmark functions experiments.

Parameter	Value
tol_{mrg}	10^{-3}
tol_m	10^{-4}
λ	0.2
γ	0.9

5.2.1. Box Plot of Minimum Values of Benchmark Mathematical Functions Found by Different Algorithms Through 10 Different Seeds

Box plots, also known as box-and-whisker plots, are diagrams that visualize the statistical distribution of data [45] (p. 2). These diagrams represent compact and easily understandable statistical metrics of the data, such as the median, Interquartile Range (IQR), distribution fences, and outliers. This allows for comparing different algorithms across numerous experiments by summarizing them in a single diagram. Figure 1 provides a guide to help interpret the box plot diagram. Chart (A) shows the conventional box plot, while chart (B) displays a specialized version known as a violin plot, which includes additional information about the distribution density of the points. However, we have used the conventional box plot in our paper because it is clearer and more elegant.

Figure 1. Structure of box plots: (A) A box plot depicting the distribution using five statistical measures: minimum, first quartile (Q1, 25th percentile), median (Q2, 50th percentile), third quartile (Q3, 75th percentile), and maximum. The whiskers extend to the smallest and largest data points within the lower and upper fences ($Q1 - 1.5 \times IQR$ and $Q3 + 1.5 \times IQR$). Data points beyond these limits are considered outliers and are marked with asterisks (*). The notch around the median represents the 95% confidence interval for the median; (B) A violin plot, a variant of the box plot that provides additional insights into the data distribution. It visualizes the probability density distribution along the y-axis. The central box denotes the interquartile range (IQR), and the white dot marks the median. Note: Red-colored text highlights key statistical measures (minimum, maximum, quartiles, and median), adapted from [45] (p. 3).

The results of the experiments on mathematical benchmark functions are presented in Figures 2–21. These figures display the box plot diagrams of the optimal minimum values (left axis) and execution durations (right axis) in seconds for the different algorithms across the 10 random generation seeds.

Figure 2. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Rastrigin function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 3. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Ackley function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 4. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Goldstein–Price function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 5. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Levy–n13 function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 6. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Himmelblau function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 7. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the three-hump camel function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 8. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Griewank function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 9. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the cross-in-tray function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 10. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the EggHolder function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 11. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Michalewicz function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 12. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Alpine function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 13. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the e Schaffer 2 function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 14. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the e Schaffer 4 function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 15. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Easom function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 16. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Shubert function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 17. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Schwefel function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 18. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Zettl function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 19. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Leon function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 20. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Drop-Wave function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Figure 21. Box plot of the minimum values and execution times obtained by various algorithms for the Langermann function. The left plot shows the best cost, while the right plot represents execution time. Different colors correspond to different algorithms, and diamond markers indicate outliers.

Mathematical Benchmarks Experiments: Box Plots Analysis

By observing the box plots in the left subplot, which visualize the minimum cost found by different algorithms, it is evident that MAGD, FMA, and SBGD achieve the most optimal values of the cost functions. They show nearly identical statistical distributions in most of the experiments, suggesting no significant difference between the three algorithms in terms of optimal solution finding. However, when we analyze the right subplot, which visualizes the execution time variability for each algorithm, we can clearly observe an additional advantage of MAGD, as it takes the shortest execution time among the three algorithms. Adam and GD significantly underperform compared to the multi-agent or swarm-based algorithms in terms of optimal value finding, as evident from the box plots of best costs. The entire distribution of the optimal costs is significantly higher than that of the superior algorithms. Adam exhibits superior capability in finding optimal solutions compared to GD in most benchmarks. However, the improvement in solution quality is considerably smaller than that achieved by multi-agent algorithms. Despite the shorter execution time of Adam and GD, they do not show a significant difference from MAGD, meaning that

their short execution time cannot compensate for their significant underperformance in terms of optimal value finding.

Regarding MAGD and SBGD, although they exhibit similar optimality-finding capabilities, SBGD often requires longer execution times. This difference is not very apparent in the visualization due to the scale of the figures and the high bias of the FMA chart. The primary challenge with SBGD lies in tuning its numerous hyperparameters to strike a balance between exploration and time efficiency. In this study, the chosen parameter settings for SBGD resulted in no significant superiority over MAGD while incurring additional time overhead. This further highlights that MAGD provides an efficient and cost-effective solution.

5.2.2. Mathematical Benchmarks Experiments Numerical Results

To make the information clearer and easier to digest, in Table 5, we present the median of the absolute difference between the true global minima and the found minima from the 10 seeds for each benchmark. For simplicity, we refer to this difference as the ‘error’ of the algorithm as illustrated in Equation (21). We prefer the median over the mean because it is not affected by outliers.

$$\text{Median_Error}_{f,a} = \text{median}\left(\left|f^* - m_{f,s_1,a}\right|, \left|f^* - m_{f,s_2,a}\right|, \dots, \left|f^* - m_{f,s_{10},a}\right|\right) \quad (21)$$

where

- Median_Error_{f,a}: The median error for the algorithm *a* when applied to the function *f*, calculated over 10 different random seeds.
- *f**: The global minimum value for function *f* based on the true global minima (this is a fixed value for the function across all seeds and algorithms).
- *m*_{f,s_i,a}: The minimum value found by algorithm *a* when applied to function *f* using the *i*-th random seed (*s_i* where *i* ∈ {1, 2, ..., 10}).

Table 5. Median of the absolute difference between the true global minima and the found minima across various optimization algorithms for standard mathematical benchmark functions over 10 different random seeds. Bold values indicate the best-performing algorithms.

Function Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Rastrigin	1.3930	0.4975	0.4975	22.9834	22.9877
Ackley	7.5376	7.5376	0.0001	19.3172	19.3171
Goldstein-Price	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	186.3059	113.5452
Levy-n13	0.0000	0.0000	0.0995	4.7850	4.8066
Himmelblau	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0023	0.0000
Three-Hump Camel	0.0597	0.0000	0.0017	0.2700	0.2091
Griewank	1.6096	1.6096	1.6219	75.7318	75.7329
Cross-in-Tray	2.0604	2.0604	2.0604	2.0608	2.0611
EggHolder	87.6805	79.2623	322.1294	844.0750	873.2270
Michalewicz	0.0001	0.0000	0.0001	0.8996	1.3997
Alpine	0.0046	0.0001	0.0012	0.0127	0.0559
Schaffer 2	0.1183	0.1182	0.1169	0.4865	0.4989
Schaffer 4	0.1742	0.1743	0.1756	0.1939	0.2063
Easom	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Shubert	6.3178	0.0015	0.0000	157.7766	157.7990
Schwefel	81.5770	77.6650	193.4469	666.3456	692.4238
Zetl	0.0000	0.0008	0.0470	0.0912	0.8460
Leon	0.0004	0.0012	0.0000	0.0003	0.0353
Drop-Wave	0.1026	0.1026	0.0065	0.8057	0.8054
Langermann	0.2211	0.0258	0.0003	4.7501	4.7487

5.2.3. Mathematical Benchmarks Experiments: Global Optimization Capability

To evaluate the new algorithm’s ability to locate global minima in the mathematical function experiments, we propose a measure called the hit rate. The hit rate counts the number of seeds where an algorithm successfully finds the global minimum, determined by whether the absolute difference between the true minimum and the minimum found by the algorithm is within a tolerance of 10^{-3} . The equations defining this measure are provided in Equations (22) and (23).

$$\text{hit} = \begin{cases} \text{True} & \text{if } |\text{opt_cost} - f^*| \leq 10^{-3}, \\ \text{False} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{22}$$

$$\text{hit rate\%} = \frac{\sum \text{hit}}{\text{number of seeds}} \times 100 \tag{23}$$

Table 6 presents the hit rate of different algorithms across various benchmark mathematical functions.

Table 6. Hit rate (in %) of various optimization algorithms across mathematical benchmark functions. The hit rate indicates the percentage of seeds for which each algorithm successfully located the global minimum. Bold values represent the best performance.

Function Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Rastrigin	10	50	50	0	0
Ackley	0	0	100	0	0
Goldstein–Price	100	100	100	30	0
Levy-n13	100	100	70	10	0
Himmelblau	100	100	100	80	100
Three-Hump Camel	80	100	50	10	30
Griewank	0	0	0	0	0
Cross-in-Tray	0	0	0	0	0
EggHolder	0	0	0	0	0
Michalewicz	100	100	100	10	0
Alpine	30	100	70	0	0
Schaffer 2	0	0	0	0	0
Schaffer 4	0	0	0	0	0
Easom	0	0	0	0	0
Shubert	10	60	100	0	0
Schwefel	10	10	0	0	0
Zettl	100	80	60	20	0
Leon	80	70	80	90	0
Drop-Wave	10	10	90	0	0
Langermann	90	90	100	0	0

Table 6 demonstrates that MAGD, FMA, and SBGD outperform GD and Adam in hit-rate performance, with similar performance observed between MAGD, FMA, and SBGD (remember that FMA is not an actual algorithm but rather multiple simultaneous executions of Adam). To substantiate these observations, we conducted a *t*-test comparing the hit ratios of MAGD with those of other algorithms. The *t*-test, also known as Student’s *t*-test, is widely used to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between two data samples. This hypothesis test uses the *t*-distribution to compute the *t*-value, which is the ratio of the observed difference in means to the variability in the data, scaled by sample sizes. Using the *t*-distribution, the *p*-value is the probability distribution function (PDF) value corresponding to the computed *t*-value. A *p*-value less than 0.05 typically indicates a significant difference between two groups [46] (p. 64).

As shown in Table 7, The *p*-values indicate no significant difference between MAGD and FMA, or between MAGD and SBGD, in terms of global optimization capability. How-

ever, the difference between MAGD and Adam, as well as between MAGD and GD, is significant. It also shows a significant difference between MAGD and all other algorithms. Compared with GD and Adam, this difference indicates a relative drawback due to MAGD’s longer duration. However, the significantly shorter execution time of MAGD compared to SBGD suggests a clear advantage, especially considering its similar effectiveness in achieving optimal solutions.

Table 7. *p*-values comparing MAGD hit rates with other algorithms for mathematical benchmark functions. Symbols (↑/↓) denote whether the difference signifies outperforming (↑) or underperforming (↓) of MAGD, while the absence of a symbol indicates no significant difference.

Comparison	<i>p</i> -Value	Significant Difference	MAGD Performance
MAGD vs. FMA	0.602	-	-
MAGD vs. SBGD	0.377	-	-
MAGD vs. Adam	0.019	Yes	↑
MAGD vs. GD	0.004	Yes	↑

5.2.4. Mathematical Benchmarks Experiments: Execution Time

Table 8 presents the median execution time spent by different algorithms to find the optimal value for each mathematical function across 10 randomly generated seeds.

Table 8. Median execution time (in seconds) across 10 random seeds for different algorithms on various mathematical benchmark functions. Bold values indicate the best performance.

Function Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Rastrigin	0.3666	5.9666	0.9698	0.0614	0.5393
Ackley	0.2912	4.7500	0.5302	0.0529	0.0253
Goldstein–Price	1.2312	12.4433	1.4645	0.3007	1.1632
Levy-N13	0.8149	15.9472	1.1628	0.1855	0.1802
Himmelblau	0.3184	4.0358	0.6075	0.1071	0.1223
Three-Hump Camel	0.5151	5.7206	0.3478	0.1715	0.3120
Griewank	0.7627	17.4497	0.3462	0.2798	0.7080
Cross-in-Tray	0.1701	5.8178	0.8469	0.2595	0.0011
Egg Holder	1.1273	49.7233	0.5644	0.5661	0.5376
Michalewicz	0.1725	2.9696	0.2883	0.0313	0.0021
Alpine	0.4941	5.2489	0.6447	0.2768	0.2611
Schaffer N2	0.8606	50.4603	0.3433	0.0251	0.5355
Schaffer N4	0.8669	50.1864	0.3567	0.0259	0.5462
Easom	0.0405	0.0404	0.0627	0.0008	0.0012
Shubert	0.9665	23.1907	1.9983	0.1549	1.2867
Schwefel	0.4966	22.5983	0.2993	0.2717	0.2537
Zettl	0.5216	6.2368	0.8068	0.4134	0.4000
Leon	0.4899	7.5925	0.5555	0.3356	0.3564
Drop-Wave	0.2668	3.2161	0.3625	0.0337	0.0283
Langermann	1.7498	33.9237	3.0435	0.2352	0.2415

Notably, FMA requires an excessively long time, which is not justified given its comparable performance to MAGD and SBGD. SBGD and MAGD require longer execution times than GD and Adam. Although the execution times of MAGD and SBGD exceed those of GD and Adam, both algorithms achieve significantly better results in finding optima. However, MAGD’s execution time remains lower than that of SBGD in most experiments, while offering comparable accuracy.

Since MAGD does not always consume less time than SBGD and the performance difference is not immediately apparent, statistical analysis is necessary to provide a broader perspective. To that end, we computed the mean, standard deviation (std), median, and 95%

Highest Density Interval (HDI), which represents the Bayesian-estimated interval where 95% of the distribution values lie [47] (p. 15). The HDI interval of execution times offers a more reliable metric for judging which algorithm takes less time. Furthermore, we conducted a *t*-test to calculate the *p*-values for the execution time differences between MAGD and each of the other benchmarks. The statistical metrics were derived from 200 samples (20 functions and 10 seeds per function) to ensure more robust results. Table 9 presents a comparison between MAGD and SBGD in terms of various statistical attributes, while Table 10 presents the *p*-values (probability of equivalent means between two samples) for the execution time differences between MAGD and each other benchmark.

Table 9. Statistical comparison of execution duration between algorithms for mathematical benchmark functions.

Comparison	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
mean ± std	0.63 ± 0.43	16.5 ± 16.74	0.76 ± 0.71	0.2 ± 0.19	0.39 ± 0.38
median	0.516	7.516	0.534	0.204	0.293
95% HDI	[0.04, 1.55]	[0.92, 51.09]	[0.01, 2.57]	[10 ⁻³ , 0.57]	[10 ⁻³ , 1.27]

Table 10. *p*-values comparing MAGD execution time with other algorithms for mathematical benchmark functions. Symbols (↑/↓) denote whether the difference signifies outperforming (↑) or underperforming (↓) of MAGD, while the absence of a symbol indicates no significant difference.

Comparison	<i>p</i> -Value	Significant Difference	MAGD Performance
MAGD vs. FMA	0.0000	Yes	↑
MAGD vs. SBGD	0.0245	Yes	↑
MAGD vs. Adam	0.0000	Yes	↓
MAGD vs. GD	0.0000	Yes	↓

Tables 9 and 10 show a significant difference between MAGD and all other algorithms. Compared to GD and Adam, this difference highlights a relative disadvantage due to MAGD’s longer duration. However, the significantly shorter execution time of MAGD compared to SBGD demonstrates a clear advantage, especially considering its similar effectiveness in achieving optimal solutions.

5.2.5. Mathematical Benchmarks Experiments: Convergence Curves

In this subsection, we present and discuss the convergence curves of selected mathematical test functions for multiple algorithms. Figures 22–26 illustrate the convergence behaviors of these algorithms, providing insight into their performance.

From the convergence curves, it is evident that MAGD demonstrates superior performance compared to Adam in many cases. While Adam requires more iterations to find the optimal value, MAGD often identifies it in the early stages due to its use of multiple searching agents. In contrast, GD is well known for its slow convergence rate compared to Adam. On the other hand, SBGD exhibits rapid convergence; however, its adaptive step size can sometimes lead to solutions that exceed the feasible range, a behavior that is typically undesirable in optimization tasks.

Figure 22. Convergence patterns of mathematical functions: Group 1.

Figure 23. Convergence patterns of mathematical functions: Group 2.

Figure 24. Convergence patterns of mathematical functions: Group 3.

Figure 25. Convergence patterns of mathematical functions: Group 4.

Figure 26. Convergence patterns of mathematical functions: Group 5.

5.3. Neural Network Training

In this subsection, we present the results of applying our algorithm to a real-world problem: neural network training. We trained shallow neural networks and evaluated their performance on various benchmark datasets. The results of our algorithm were compared with those of FMA, SBGD, Adam and GD.

5.3.1. Experimental Design

The neural network consists of three layers: an input layer, a hidden layer, and an output layer. The input layer has weights shaped as (input_features_number, hidden_neurons_number). The hidden layer has a number of neurons equal to $(2/3) \times \text{input_features_number} + 1$. The output layer contains one neuron for regression tasks and a variable number of neurons for classification tasks. The activation function is linear for regression and softmax for classification. Table 11 lists the datasets used in the experiments.

Table 11. Experimental datasets.

No.	Dataset Name	Features	Samples	Task
1	Iris	4	150	Classification
2	Wine	13	178	Classification
3	Breast-Cancer-Wisconsin	30	569	Classification
4	Digits	64	1797	Classification
5	Pima-Indians-Diabetes	8	768	Classification
6	Connectionist Bench	8	208	Classification
7	Glass Identification	9	214	Classification
8	Balance Scale	4	625	Classification
9	Banknote Authentication	4	1372	Classification
10	Adult	14	48,842	Classification
11	Diabetes	10	442	Regression
12	California Housing	8	20,640	Regression
13	Boston Housing	13	506	Regression
14	Auto MPG	7	398	Regression
15	Concrete Compressive Strength	8	1030	Regression
16	Energy Efficiency	8	768	Regression
17	Yacht Hydrodynamics	7	308	Regression
18	Forest Fires	12	517	Regression
19	Airfoil Self-Noise	5	1503	Regression
20	Concrete Slump Test	7	103	Regression

The hyperparameters used for each algorithm during neural network training are presented in Table 12. Algorithm-specific parameters for MAGD and SBGD are detailed in Tables 13 and 14, respectively.

Table 12. Hyperparameters settings for neural network training across different algorithms. The symbol “-” indicates that the parameter is absent in the respective algorithm.

Algorithm	N_{agents}	α	t_{max}	ϵ_{conv}	β_1	β_2	ϵ
MAGD	10	0.03	500	1×10^{-4}	0.9	0.999	1×10^{-8}
FMA	10	0.03	500	1×10^{-4}	0.9	0.999	1×10^{-8}
SBGD	10	3	500	1×10^{-4}	-	-	-
Adam	1	0.03	500	1×10^{-4}	0.9	0.999	1×10^{-8}
GD	1	0.03	500	1×10^{-4}	-	-	-

Table 13. MAGD exclusive hyperparameters settings for neural network training.

T_{conv}	T_{red}
10	10

Table 14. SBGD exclusive hyperparameters settings for neural network training.

γ	λ	tol_{merg}	tol_m
0.9	0.2	1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-4}

All algorithms were initialized with weights randomly generated within the range $[-1, 1]$. For SBGD, FMA, and MAGD, the number of agents was set to 10, a reduced value due to resource constraints. Datasets were shuffled and split into 70% training and 30% testing sets. To ensure consistency, the random seed for weight initialization was set to 42 across all algorithms.

5.3.2. Results of Neural Network Training

In this section, we present the results of training neural networks using four algorithms and FMA, comparing their performance in terms of two aspects: training accuracy and execution time.

Training Performance and Accuracy

To compare the algorithms, we define the evaluation metrics used for this analysis, which are presented in Equations (24)–(26).

- Mean Squared Error (MSE): MSE measures the average of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. It quantifies the model's prediction error, with lower values indicating a better fit.

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (24)$$

- Accuracy Score: Accuracy score is the ratio that measures the probability that the model correctly predicts the target variable.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i = \hat{y}_i) \quad (25)$$

- Coefficient of Determination (R^2): R^2 indicates the capability of the regression model to explain the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables (features). A value closer to 1 suggests a better fit. The R^2 value typically ranges from 0 to 1, but it can be less than 0 in some cases, indicating that the model poorly fits the data.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (26)$$

where

- n is the total number of data points.
- y_i is the true label for the i -th data point.
- \hat{y}_i is the predicted label for the i -th data point.
- $(y_i = \hat{y}_i)$ is an indicator function that equals 1 if $y_i = \hat{y}_i$ (i.e., the prediction is correct) and 0 otherwise.
- \bar{y} is the mean of the true labels.

For the accuracy score metric, we will consider the models' accuracy on the test datasets. However, for the MSE metric, we will compare algorithms using both training and testing datasets. While our primary focus is on developing an optimization algorithm for neural network training, where the MSE on the test data is more relevant, we also compare performance on the training data. This comparison highlights the algorithm's potential for broader applications, demonstrating its general-purpose capabilities beyond just the specific task of neural network optimization.

Many researchers, such as Liu et al. [48] (p. 8), argue that minimizing the training error too aggressively can lead to overfitting. While this is true in some cases, it is not always the expected outcome. In general, achieving a smaller training error often leads to better accuracy on both the training and testing sets. However, when there is a significant gap between training and testing performance, it can be a sign of issues such as inefficient data splitting, insufficient data, or other factors like outliers in the training set or overly complex models. Our results support this hypothesis.

This risk can be mitigated using established techniques, including regularization, dropout, and data augmentation. In our experiments, we employed $L2$ regularization, which reduces model complexity by modifying the training cost function to include a penalty on trainable weights. It is important to note that while this technique can help mitigate overfitting risks, it does not completely eliminate the problem. The formula for $L2$ regularization is shown in Equation (27).

$$L2 \text{ Regularization} = \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p w_j^2 \quad (27)$$

where

- λ is the regularization parameter (also known as the shrinkage or penalty term).
- p is the number of features or weights.
- w_j represents the j -th weight in the model.
- $\sum_{j=1}^p w_j^2$ is the sum of the squared weights, which penalizes large weights.

Thus, the task is to minimize the cost function shown in Equation (28).

$$\text{Cost} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p w_j^2 \quad (28)$$

Our findings indicate that in most cases, more optimal training errors lead to better generalization accuracy. We observe an increasing linear trend for testing error versus training error, as shown in Figure 27. Figure 27 has five axes, each representing the variance of testing error versus training error. For clearer visualization, the trend was fitted using Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC), a linear regression technique that is strengthened by features designed to protect the model from being affected by outliers [49,50] (p. 2). The red cross symbol represents outliers, defined as data points where the residual distance (predicted value – actual value) is greater than 1. We observe that larger testing errors for larger training errors are not typical, but rather exceptional. There are at most two outliers, if any, out of 20 experiments.

Tables 15 and 16 compare the training costs achieved by the four algorithms in addition to FMA. The bold values indicate the least error among all algorithms. FMA achieves the least error in almost all datasets, but since we consider FMA as merely multiple executions of algorithms, it is not fair to judge its superiority here, as it consumes significantly longer time, as discussed in the next paragraph. Therefore, we will highlight the least error among the remaining algorithms (MAGD, SBGD, Adam, and GD) with * and use this to evaluate the superiority of these four algorithms. Looking at the training error values in Table 15, both MAGD and Adam demonstrate superior performance, with MAGD achieving slightly better solutions in most cases. Although this difference between Adam and MAGD is not statistically significant (a t -test is unnecessary for this comparison), practical applications may still value these small improvements. Minor increases in classification accuracy or R^2 in machine learning can have a significant practical impact, particularly in fields like medical diagnostics [51] (p. 4) and [52].

Figure 27. Trend of testing error variance as a function of training error variance in neural network training tasks.

Table 15. Training error values obtained by MAGD, FMA, SBDG, Adam, and GD for each dataset. Bolded values indicate the best result. ‘*’ denotes the best result among the algorithms excluding FMA, as FMA is not always the best.

Dataset Name	MAGD	FMA	SBDG	Adam	GD
Iris	0.2114	0.2084	0.5458	0.2084 *	0.6506
Wine	0.0872	0.0869	0.3065	0.0869 *	0.3303
Breast Cancer Wisconsin	0.0688 *	0.0688	0.3058	0.0689	0.3588
Digits	0.2574 *	0.2574	1.5106	0.2599	1.7374
Pima Indians Diabetes	0.4480 *	0.4470	0.5293	0.4510	0.5441
Connectionist Bench	0.0855 *	0.0852	1.3007	0.0863	1.0639
Glass Identification	0.6890 *	0.6890	1.2473	0.7306	1.2543
Balance Scale	0.3320 *	0.3320	0.5087	0.3521	0.7724
Banknote Authentication	0.1027	0.1021	0.3473	0.1023 *	0.5598
Adult	0.3333 *	0.3333	2.5611	0.3333 *	2.4446
Diabetes	0.4137 *	0.4022	0.6237	0.4194	0.5368
California Housing	0.3351	0.3328	0.5682	0.3335 *	0.4378
Boston Housing	0.1267	0.1252	0.5145	0.1256 *	0.3396
Auto MPG	0.1332 *	0.1324	0.2308	0.1337	0.2324
Concrete Compressive Strength	0.1678 *	0.1660	0.4276	0.1682	0.3844
Energy Efficiency	0.0667 *	0.0651	0.1787	0.0753	0.1316
Yacht Hydrodynamics	0.0681	0.0596	0.4158	0.0672 *	0.3596
Forest Fires	0.4871 *	0.4801	1.5411	0.5106	1.4490
Airfoil Self-Noise	0.2983 *	0.2983	0.6478	0.3406	0.4724
Concrete Slump Test	0.0391 *	0.0361	0.1948	0.0405	0.1354

Table 16. Testing error values obtained by MAGD, FMA, SBGD, Adam, and GD for each dataset. Bolded values indicate the best result. ‘*’ denotes the best result among the algorithms excluding FMA, as FMA is not always the best.

Dataset Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Iris	0.1756	0.1723	0.5853	0.1723 *	0.6774
Wine	0.0914 *	0.0914	0.3137	0.0914 *	0.281
Breast Cancer Wisconsin	0.1443	0.1443	0.3590	0.1434 *	0.3865
Digits	0.3250 *	0.3250	1.5970	0.3269	1.8109
Pima Indians Diabetes	0.5381	0.5378	0.5264 *	0.5340	0.5449
Connectionist Bench	0.8415	0.8075	1.3797	0.7793 *	1.4082
Glass Identification	1.2559	1.1650	1.3674	1.1613 *	1.4225
Balance Scale	0.3393 *	0.3393	0.4879	0.3603	0.7383
Banknote Authentication	0.1013	0.1007	0.3460	0.1009 *	0.5542
Adult	0.3430 *	0.3430	2.5628	0.3430 *	2.4413
Diabetes	0.5584	0.6359	0.5827	0.5825	0.4455 *
California Housing	0.3338	0.3303	0.5903	0.3314 *	0.4498
Boston Housing	0.1522 *	0.1533	0.4468	0.1644	0.2982
Auto MPG	0.1173	0.1133	0.1941	0.1165 *	0.1926
Concrete Compressive Strength	0.2063 *	0.2070	0.4983	0.2086	0.4252
Energy Efficiency	0.0670 *	0.0661	0.1706	0.0728	0.1229
Yacht Hydrodynamics	0.0705	0.0613	0.3533	0.0695 *	0.3237
Forest Fires	3.8441	3.2475	0.5428	2.9355	0.4613 *
Airfoil Self-Noise	0.2906 *	0.2906	0.6447	0.3325	0.4701
Concrete Slump Test	0.0973	0.0756	0.3574	0.0829 *	0.2542

GD and SBGD perform substantially worse in training cost optimization than Adam and MAGD, which raises the question of why SBGD, which performs well in low-dimensional mathematical function tests, falls short in neural network training. One possible explanation is that SBGD has not demonstrated superior performance in high-dimensional problems, as noted in its original study [15]; the mathematical functions tested here were limited to two dimensions, while neural network cost functions have a larger number of dimensions. Additionally, SBGD’s performance is sensitive to its numerous hyperparameters, which can cause premature convergence and limit solution quality. Our experiments also used a relatively small number of agents (10) for SBGD due to computational constraints, which could affect its efficacy.

In Table 16, we again omit FMA and refer to the best results among MAGD, SBGD, Adam, and GD with *. The results show consistent patterns between test error and training error. SBGD has the least error in only 1 dataset out of 20, GD in 2 datasets, while MAGD and Adam achieve the best values, with MAGD slightly underperforming Adam. However, this underperformance is not significant, as MAGD has the best values in 8 datasets out of 20, while Adam has the best values in 11 datasets out of 20. Nevertheless, since MAGD performs best in terms of training error, it still holds great promise for optimization problems where local minima arise. Additionally, a lower mean square error does not always correlate with worse classification or regression accuracy. These metrics are represented in Tables 17 and 18. Table 17 compares the test accuracy of different algorithms on classification datasets, while Table 18 compares the R^2 scores for different algorithms on various regression datasets. The same configuration applies here as for the training and testing errors, where we omit FMA and refer to the best score among MAGD, SBGD, Adam, and GD with *. Note that the maximum value is the best, in contrast to MSE.

Table 17. Accuracy scores of different algorithms across various classification datasets. Bold values highlight the highest accuracy achieved on each dataset. (*) indicates the maximum accuracy among all algorithms except FMA.

Dataset Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Iris	100% *	100%	80%	100% *	78%
Wine	98% *	98%	94%	98% *	98% *
Breast-Cancer-Wisconsin	96% *	96%	94%	96% *	96% *
Digits	97% *	97%	82%	97% *	77%
Pima-Indians-Diabetes	79% *	79%	77%	76%	77%
Connectionist Bench	78% *	76%	75%	76%	76%
Glass Identification	62%	57%	48%	55%	45%
Balance Scale	90% *	90%	90% *	87%	80%
Banknote Authentication	99% *	98%	90%	98%	85%
Adult	85% *	85%	79%	85% *	80%

Table 18. R^2 scores of different algorithms across various regression datasets. Bold values highlight the highest score achieved on each dataset. (*) indicates the maximum score among all algorithms except FMA.

Dataset Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Diabetes	0.41	0.32	0.33	0.38	0.50 *
California Housing	0.71 *	0.71	0.45	0.71 *	0.58
Boston Housing	0.89 *	0.89	0.56	0.88	0.72
Auto MPG	0.89 *	0.90	0.79	0.89 *	0.79
Concrete Strength	0.85 *	0.85	0.56	0.85 *	0.63
Energy Efficiency	0.96 *	0.97	0.84	0.95	0.89
Yacht Hydrodynamics	0.98 *	0.98	0.58	0.98 *	0.62
Forest Fires	−23.66	−19.46	−1.58	−17.24	− 0.98 *
Airfoil Self-Noise	0.79 *	0.79	0.37	0.72	0.55
Concrete Slump Test	0.95	0.96	0.74	0.96 *	0.82

The results demonstrate the superiority of MAGD, particularly in classification tasks, where it achieves the highest test scores across all classification datasets. In regression tasks, while FMA slightly outperforms MAGD, FMA is excluded from our comparison. In most cases, MAGD’s lower training error corresponds to superior generalization, with the exception of the “Forest Fires” dataset.

Classification Test Results Discussion: The tables reveal the underperformance of SBGD and GD. Since FMA is excluded from the comparison, the focus is on comparing MAGD and Adam. To formalize the comparison, the following symbol is introduced:

- $A_1 \succ A_2$: indicates that algorithm A_1 absolutely outperforms A_2 .

Using this notation, the superiority ratio of algorithm A_1 , denoted $P_{super} \in [-100\%, 100\%]$, is defined in Equation (29). This metric quantifies the proportion of datasets where A_1 outperforms A_2 , adjusted for cases of underperformance. A negative value indicates underperformance, while 0% denotes equivalence.

$$P_{super}(A_1 \succ A_2) = 100 \cdot \frac{\sum(score_{A_1,i} > score_{A_2,i}) - \sum(score_{A_1,i} < score_{A_2,i})}{n} \quad (29)$$

Here,

- A_1 and A_2 : the algorithms being compared.
- n : total number of datasets.
- $score_{A,i}$: performance score of algorithm A on the i -th dataset.

Table 19 summarizes the superiority ratio of MAGD over Adam in classification tasks.

Table 19. Comparison of MAGD and Adam in terms of the superiority ratio in classification tasks P_{super} .

Comparison	P_{super}
MAGD \succ Adam	50%

While MAGD achieves the highest accuracy across all datasets, its accuracy is comparable to Adam's in 50% of the experiments. Thus, MAGD exhibits a 50% improvement ratio over Adam.

Regression Results Discussion: In regression tasks, MAGD achieves the maximum R^2 score in 50% of the datasets, with Adam also achieving the maximum in 50%. GD attains the highest R^2 score in two cases, whereas SBGD achieves none. To clarify MAGD's absolute superiority, Table 20 reports the superiority ratio of MAGD compared to Adam and GD in regression tasks. MAGD provides 20% improvement ratio over Adam, and 50% over GD.

Table 20. Comparison of MAGD, Adam, and GD in terms of the superiority ratio in regression tasks P_{super} .

Comparison	P_{super}
MAGD \succ Adam	20%
MAGD \succ GD	50%

The results of neural network training indicate that even when testing error is higher, MAGD often outperforms SBGD, Adam, and GD, further validating its effectiveness.

Training Duration Evaluation

This paragraph evaluates the execution time of the proposed algorithm compared to other methods as shown in Table 21 that reports the mean number of convergence iterations for each algorithm to train the neural networks. One can observe that SBGD consumes the shortest time for neural network training compared to the other algorithms. This behavior contrasts with its performance on mathematical functions. The reason for SBGD's faster training lies in its rapid convergence, as shown in Table 22. However, this rapid convergence results in lower performance scores and shorter execution times, primarily due to the numerous hyperparameters that require tuning to control the algorithm's convergence behavior.

Among the algorithms, FMA requires the longest execution time. However, the extreme time overhead of FMA is not greatly correlated with its performance. MAGD consumes the longest time among the remaining algorithms (SBGD, Adam, and GD), but this extended execution time is correlated with its superior performance scores. Despite this observation, statistical inference suggests the differences in execution time between MAGD and GD or Adam algorithms are not statistically significant, as elaborated in the next analysis and discussion.

Table 21. Performance comparison of execution time (in seconds) between MAGD and other methods for neural network training. The shortest execution time for each dataset is bolded.

Dataset Name	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
Iris	2.0073	7.4819	0.1353	0.7797	0.7647
Wine	1.8196	7.8309	0.1648	0.8613	0.8372
Breast Cancer-Wisconsin	2.2510	10.2646	0.4303	1.1015	1.0794
Digits	11.5828	53.5168	3.0308	6.4266	6.6754
Pima-Indians-Diabetes	1.9711	8.9067	0.4297	1.0061	1.0352
Connectionist Bench	2.6584	16.9505	0.4844	2.5504	2.4633
Glass Identification	1.3941	7.9909	0.2585	0.9120	0.9146
Balance Scale	1.7598	8.3114	0.1932	0.9340	0.8763
Banknote Authentication	1.8752	9.4750	0.5279	1.0181	0.9934
Adult	160.4189	802.5116	40.1365	89.4274	88.4908
Diabetes	8.0211	7.0622	0.1925	0.8138	0.7878
California Housing	1.9058	57.6776	0.24739	7.1823	8.1433
Boston Housing	1.7830	7.3301	0.2278	0.8431	0.8244
Auto MPG	1.2297	6.7451	0.1115	0.7248	0.7024
Concrete Compressive Strength	1.7650	7.5510	0.1668	0.8032	0.7982
Energy Efficiency	2.2301	7.2413	0.1361	0.7633	0.7519
Yacht Hydrodynamics	1.088	6.6225	0.1232	0.7054	0.6873
Forest Fires	2.1748	8.4036	0.2031	0.9233	0.8603
Airfoil Self-Noise	2.0718	7.6019	0.1645	0.8126	0.8074
Concrete Slump Test	1.6497	6.4361	0.1177	0.6745	0.6580

Table 22. Statistical comparison of iterations required for convergence for different algorithms in neural network training.

Algorithm	Mean \pm Std. Dev.
MAGD	499 \pm 1
FMA	500 \pm 0
SBGD	10 \pm 4
Adam	500 \pm 0
GD	500 \pm 0

Statistical Analysis of Training Duration: To derive insights from the statistical results of the different algorithms, statistical features such as the mean, standard deviation (std), median, and the 90% Highest Density Interval (HDI) are presented in Table 23. We opted for the 90% HDI instead of the 95% HDI due to the presence of an outlier in the Adult dataset, where all algorithms exhibit large deviations from their distributions. This outlier impacts the accuracy of the highest density interval estimation when using a 95% interval.

Table 23. Statistical comparison between the execution duration of different algorithms for neural network training.

Comparison	MAGD	FMA	SBGD	Adam	GD
mean \pm std	10.6 \pm 34.5	52.8 \pm 172.6	2.5 \pm 8.7	6.0 \pm 19.2	6.0 \pm 19.0
median	1.9	7.9	0.2	0.9	0.8
90% HDI	[1.1, 11.6]	[6.4, 57.7]	[0.1, 3.0]	[0.7, 7.2]	[0.7, 8.1]

Additionally, a *t*-test was conducted to evaluate the significance of differences between the algorithms (*p*-value). The *t*-test results, presented in Table 24.

Table 24. *p*-values comparing MAGD execution time with other algorithms for neural network training before removing the outlier dataset. Symbols (↑/↓) denote whether the difference signifies outperforming (↑) or underperforming (↓) of MAGD, while the absence of a symbol indicates no significant difference.

Comparison	<i>p</i> -Value	Significant Difference	MAGD Performance
MAGD vs. FMA	0.31	No	-
MAGD vs. SBGD	0.33	No	-
MAGD vs. Adam	0.6	No	-
MAGD vs. GD	0.6	No	-

Tables 23 and 24 indicate that FMA’s mean duration is significantly longer than that of the other algorithms. Adam and GD exhibit approximately equivalent mean durations and standard deviations. SBGD has the shortest execution time, while MAGD takes slightly longer than Adam, with a somewhat broader range within which 90% of the execution times fall. Given that Adam is the most competitive algorithm to MAGD, determining the differences in execution time relative to Adam is of primary interest.

Table 23 initially suggests no statistically significant difference between the execution times of MAGD and the other algorithms. However, these values appear inconsistent with observations, as the differences in execution times are visually apparent. The unreliability of the initial *t*-test results stems from the presence of outliers, which can distort the findings. To address this, the outlier case (Adult dataset) was removed, and the *t*-test was repeated. The revised *p*-values, shown in Table 25, yield more interpretable results.

Table 25. *p*-values comparing MAGD execution time with other algorithms for neural network training after removing the outlier dataset. Symbols (↑/↓) denote whether the difference signifies outperforming (↑) or underperforming (↓) of MAGD, while the absence of a symbol indicates no significant difference.

Comparison	<i>p</i> -Value	Significant Difference	MAGD Performance
MAGD vs. FMA	0.007	Yes	↑
MAGD vs. SBGD	0.002	Yes	↓
MAGD vs. Adam	0.141	No	-
MAGD vs. GD	0.172	No	-

The updated results demonstrate that the difference in execution time between MAGD and Adam is not statistically significant. This aligns with our earlier conclusion in the time complexity Section 4.2.1, which asserts that as $d \gg N_0$ (a scenario that occurs frequently in our case), or $t_{max} \gg N_0$ (in our case, $500 \gg 10$), MAGD’s time cost approaches Adam’s execution time.

Adam with the Same Time Budget vs. MAGD

The Adam algorithm, one of the most widely used optimization methods in machine learning, warrants a comparative analysis to assess whether it can achieve similar performance to MAGD when allocated an equivalent execution time. Such an investigation is crucial for evaluating whether Adam, with extended iterations, can match MAGD’s performance, potentially making MAGD unnecessary in time-sensitive applications.

Initially, all algorithms were executed for a maximum of 500 iterations. To ensure a fair comparison between single-agent and multi-agent approaches, Adam’s maximum iterations were extended to 750 and 1000 in separate experiments. Table 26 displays the execution times for MAGD (with 500 iterations) and Adam across these three configurations. Additionally, Table 27 provides the mean number of convergence epochs (\pm standard devi-

ation) and the mean execution time (\pm standard deviation) for MAGD and Adam under the respective experimental setups.

Table 26. Execution time comparison among MAGD and Adam variants for neural network training across datasets. Bold values indicate the shortest time for each dataset.

Dataset Name	MAGD-500	Adam-500	Adam-750	Adam-1000
Iris	2.01	0.78	1.19	2.05
Wine	1.82	0.86	1.24	2.16
Breast-Cancer-Wisconsin	2.25	1.10	1.71	3
Digits	11.58	6.43	11.31	21.73
Pima-Indians-Diabetes	1.97	1.01	2.03	3
Connectionist Bench	2.66	2.55	3.86	9.38
Glass Identification	1.39	0.91	1.34	3.41
Balance Scale	1.76	0.93	1.38	2.96
Banknote Authentication	1.88	1.02	1.53	3.37
Adult	160.42	89.43	166.8	206.56
Diabetes	1.95	0.81	1.22	1.64
California Housing	8.02	7.18	12.17	15.99
Boston Housing	1.91	0.84	1.27	1.78
Auto MPG	1.78	0.72	1.11	1.53
Concrete Compressive Strength	1.23	0.80	1.27	1.71
Energy Efficiency	1.77	0.76	1.25	1.64
Yacht Hydrodynamics	1.09	0.70	1.1	1.49
Forest Fires	2.17	0.92	1.51	1.93
Airfoil Self-Noise	2.07	0.81	1.27	1.66
Concrete Slump Test	1.65	0.67	1.05	1.49

Table 27. Mean and standard deviation of execution times for MAGD and Adam with varying maximum iterations for neural network training.

Algorithm	Convergence Epochs	Execution Time (Mean \pm std)
MAGD-500	499 \pm 1	10.57 \pm 34.47
Adam-500	500 \pm 0	5.96 \pm 19.23
Adam-750	750 \pm 0	10.78 \pm 35.93
Adam-1000	997 \pm 13	14.42 \pm 44.39

From Table 27, we can see that Adam's execution time is approximately the same as MAGD's when Adam is run for 750 epochs.

Table 28 presents the accuracy scores of MAGD and Adam for 500, 750, and 1000 iterations, offering further insight into their relative performance. Additionally, Table 29 shows the R^2 scores for MAGD and Adam across multiple datasets with varying maximum iterations.

To evaluate the performance of MAGD compared to Adam with extended iterations, we examine their absolute superiority ratio P_{super} that is computed according to Equation (29) in terms of accuracy score across classification datasets and R^2 score across regression datasets, in addition to introducing a second ratio called the average time penalty, ATP , which quantifies the average of additional computational time incurred by one algorithm relative to another. It is calculated as:

$$ATP(A_1, A_2) = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{T_{A_1} - T_{A_2}}{T_{A_2}}, \quad (30)$$

where T_{A_1} and T_{A_2} are the execution times of A_1 and A_2 , respectively, and n is the number

of observations. Thus, $T_{A_1} = T_{A_2} + ATP(A_1, A_2) \cdot T_{A_2}$. A negative ATP value indicates that A_1 is computationally faster than A_2 .

Table 28. Accuracy scores of MAGD with 500 maximum iterations compared to Adam with 500, 750, and 1000 maximum iterations across various classification datasets. Bold values indicate the highest accuracy achieved for each dataset.

Dataset Name	MAGD-500	Adam-500	Adam-750	Adam-1000
Iris	100%	100%	100%	100%
Wine	98%	98%	98%	98%
Breast-Cancer-Wisconsin	96%	96%	96%	96%
Digits	97%	97%	97%	97%
Pima-Indians-Diabetes	79%	76%	78%	76%
Connectionist Bench	78%	76%	76%	76%
Glass Identification	62%	55%	54%	58%
Balance Scale	90%	87%	88%	88%
Banknote Authentication	99%	98%	98%	98%
Adult	85%	85%	85%	85%

Table 29. R^2 scores of MAGD with 500 maximum iterations compared to Adam with 500, 750, and 1000 maximum iterations across various regression datasets. Bold values indicate the highest score achieved for each dataset.

Dataset Name	MAGD-500	Adam-500	Adam-750	Adam-1000
Diabetes	0.41	0.38	0.36	0.36
California Housing	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.71
Boston Housing	0.89	0.88	0.88	0.88
Auto MPG	0.89	0.89	0.90	0.90
Concrete Strength	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.85
Energy Efficiency	0.96	0.95	0.95	0.96
Yacht Hydrodynamics	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98
Forest Fires	−23.66	−17.24	−19.25	−19.81
Airfoil Self-Noise	0.79	0.72	0.72	0.72
Concrete Slump Test	0.95	0.96	0.97	0.97

We computed both the P_{super} and the corresponding ATP for MAGD considering all datasets for each types of the tasks, means $n = 10$ for fixed 500 maximum iterations and Adam for three different values of maximum iterations and the results are presented in Table 30 for classification tasks and in Table 31 for regression tasks.

Table 30. Comparison of MAGD for fixed maximum iterations and Adam with varying maximum iterations using ATP (average time penalty) and P_{super} (performance superiority) in classification tasks.

Comparison	$ATP (MAGD, Adam)$	$P_{super} (MAGD \succ Adam)$
MAGD-500 vs. Adam-500	0.86	50%
MAGD-500 vs. Adam-750	0.17	50%
MAGD-500 vs. Adam-1000	−0.36	50%

Table 31. Comparison of MAGD for fixed maximum iterations and Adam with varying maximum iterations using ATP (average time penalty) and P_{super} (performance superiority) in regression tasks.

Comparison	$ATP (MAGD, Adam)$	$P_{super} (MAGD \succ Adam)$
MAGD-500 vs. Adam-500	1.1	20%
MAGD-500 vs. Adam-750	0.34	10%
MAGD-500 vs. Adam-1000	−0.67	0%

Tables 30 and 31 demonstrate that MAGD consistently maintains its superiority in classification tasks, even when Adam is allocated a longer time budget. Specifically, Table 30 shows that MAGD outperforms Adam in classification tasks, despite Adam receiving a longer execution time. Table 31 further reveals that when Adam is given 750 maximum iterations, resulting in a similar time consumption as MAGD with 500 iterations, MAGD still achieves a 10% improvement. Even when Adam is granted 1000 iterations and a longer execution time than MAGD, it performs only equivalently to MAGD, underscoring the role of multi-agent initialization in improving optimization results.

6. Conclusions

In this study, we introduced a novel multi-start optimization algorithm, Multi-Agent Gradient Descent (MAGD), motivated by the need to address challenges in machine learning where gradient-based algorithms often struggle with local optima. By adaptively pruning underperforming agents, MAGD achieves a balance between simplicity and computational efficiency.

Theoretical analysis demonstrated that MAGD maintains computational efficiency comparable to single-agent gradient-based algorithms in scenarios where the dimensionality of the problem or the number of iterations significantly exceeds the number of agents. This scalability highlights MAGD's suitability for high-dimensional and extended optimization tasks.

We evaluated MAGD on mathematical non-convex problems (20 benchmark 2D mathematical functions) and neural network training (10 regression and 10 classification datasets). MAGD consistently outperformed GD and Adam, even when Adam was given equivalent or longer time budgets, and demonstrated optimization performance comparable to Swarm-Based Gradient Descent (SBGD) and Fixed Multi-Agent Adam (FMA). However, MAGD showed significant advantages in execution time over both SBGD and FMA, while requiring minimal hyperparameter tuning and being easier to implement compared to SBGD. These results highlight MAGD's practicality and robustness.

In neural network training experiments, where the number of iterations greatly exceeded the number of agents, MAGD exhibited execution times statistically comparable to GD and Adam. In contrast, for mathematical function experiments involving a high number of agents and low-dimensional problems, MAGD achieved significantly slower execution times than single-agent methods. These findings align with our theoretical analysis.

Despite these promising results, MAGD has limitations. It does not guarantee finding the global minimum, and although we theoretically demonstrated its effectiveness in high-dimensional optimization problems, this claim was not empirically verified. Our experiments were restricted to 2D mathematical functions and shallow neural networks with low to medium-dimensional datasets.

In the future, we plan to test MAGD on high-dimensional mathematical problems and deep neural network training to validate its efficiency and scalability. Additionally, we aim to compare MAGD with a broader range of multi-start optimization variants to provide a more comprehensive evaluation. Further research should also focus on improving its global optimization capabilities and exploring its applicability to broader optimization tasks beyond machine learning.

We believe MAGD's simplicity, reduced reliance on hyperparameters, and competitive performance make it a robust alternative to Adam in machine learning and deep learning applications. Often, well-designed, simple solutions prove to be the most effective or at least highly competitive.

Supplementary Materials: The Colab notebook for implementing the algorithms for both mathematical functions and neural network training tasks is provided at the link below. This notebook includes the core classes and functionalities of the proposed algorithms, along with demonstrations for mathematical functions and neural network training. While the notebook does not include the full code for generating all experiments and results presented in this study, it provides sufficient resources to reproduce the experiments using the basic classes and the hyperparameter settings described earlier in this paper. <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1IcpeAa1hNaG-ns6oT1CKOTdmojLXVht?usp=sharing>, accessed on 26 January 2025.

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